

African music through the eyes of the earliest travelers to West Africa: *The Description and historical account of the rich golden kingdom of Guinea* by Pieter de Marees (1602)

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Abstract

Beschryvinge ende historische vant Gout Koninckrijck van Gunea (The description and historical tale of the Golden Kingdom of Africa), written by the Dutch merchant Pieter de Marees upon his return from the African regions on the Gulf of Guinea and published in 1602, was one of the first travel chronicles of Africa whose text and illustrations were based on the author's direct experience of the region. *Beschryvinge*, translated into the most important European languages at that time, including Latin, was widely read throughout Europe and it became one of the most cited works on Africa by the later authors and compilers of travel literature. De Marees described geography, flora and fauna of the different regions that he explored, and the customs and culture of the inhabitants that he encountered, including their music: several passages are devoted to the musical instruments of the region and their performance technique, as well as the context in which music was performed.

La musica africana attraverso gli occhi dei primi viaggiatori dell'Africa occidentale: Descrizione e resoconto storico del ricco regno d'oro della Guinea di Pieter de Marees (1602). *Beschryvinge ende historische vant Gout Koninckrijck van Gunea* (Descrizione e racconto storico del Regno d'Oro d'Africa), scritto dal mercante olandese Pieter de Marees al suo ritorno dalle regioni africane del Golfo di Guinea e pubblicato nel 1602, fu una delle prime cronache di viaggio sull'Africa il cui testo e le cui illustrazioni si basavano sull'esperienza diretta

dell'autore nella regione. Il Beschryvinge, tradotto nelle principali lingue europee dell'epoca, compreso il latino, fu ampiamente letto in tutta Europa e divenne una delle opere sull'Africa più citate dai successivi autori e compilatori di letteratura di viaggio. De Marees descrisse la geografia, la flora e la fauna delle diverse regioni che esplorò, i costumi e la cultura degli abitanti che incontrò, compresa la loro musica: diversi passaggi sono dedicati agli strumenti musicali della regione e alla loro tecnica di esecuzione, nonché al contesto in cui la musica veniva eseguita.

The chronicles and accounts written by the travelers visiting Africa in 16th and 17th centuries became the main means allowing the Western audience to approach its most unknown regions and begin to learn not only about the geography, flora and fauna of the different regions explored, but also about the customs and culture of their inhabitants. Of course, among the elements that aroused the travelers' curiosity there were also sound events: in the chronicles we find more or less detailed annotations on the organological features and sonorities of musical instruments and sound objects never seen before, on the ways the musicians played and related to each other, and on the rituals and ceremonies where musical and sound events took place.

However, even if this new information made it possible to open a window on hitherto unknown reality, the enormous cultural gap between European culture and that of the natives Africans meant that the information included in the geographic literature was superficial, fanciful, full of common places and prejudices that resulted from looking at this new reality using the same point of view and cultural coordinates as the Old Continent.¹

In this paper I would like to focus on the *Description and Historical Account of the Rich Golden Kingdom of Guinea* (*Beschryvinge ende historische verhael vant Gout Koninckrijck van Guinea*) by the Dutch trader Pieter de Marees, based on his expedition to West Africa in 1600 and 1601 and published in Amsterdam in 1602.² We know very little about the author, except that he visited the West African coast in several occasions, at a time when the European commercial interests, mainly Dutch and Portuguese, looked at the Guinea regions with increasing interest.

De Marees's text, like many other early modern travel accounts, was also translated into the important European languages. A German and a Latin translations by Gotthard Arthus were published in Frankfurt am Main in 1604 in the collection *Les Petits Voyages* by the Theodore De Bry;³ a French translation in Amsterdam in 1605, and an abridged

¹ For issues related to the use of European sources for African history see van Dantzig and Jones 1987: 4; Law 1987.

² Pieter de Marees, *Beschryvinge ende historische verhael vant Gout Koninckrijck van Guinea*, Amsterdam, Cornelis Claesz, 1602. Modern English edition by van Dantzig and Jones 1987. See also Ammissah 1968.

³ De Marees 1604. See the project on the *Grands and Petit Voyages* by De Bry edited by the University of Geneva and the Bodmer Library: <<https://bodmerlab.unige.ch/recits-et-images/debry/#/grands-voyages/Preface>>.

English version was published in 1625.⁴ A new edition of the original version of the book was edited in 1912 by L'Honoré Naber.⁵ Thanks to these translations and to the plates included in the original text, the *Description* by de Marees became one of the most influential texts in shaping the attitudes and imagery of Europeans regarding that land.

In the 1602 original edition, the *Description* consists of 258 pages with a copperplate on the title page and 18 copperplate illustrations scattered throughout. The text is divided into three parts: the overview of the journey from Holland to Guinea («through the Canary Island, past Capo de Verde, along the Malaguetta Coast, down to Capo de Trespuntas, where the Gold Coast begins»), the description of Guinea, and then of Benin with the return journey to Holland.⁶ At the end of the book there is a kind of dictionary and phrasebook of African words and expressions from the Gold Coast translated into Dutch.

Not everything in de Marees's narrative is the result of the direct observations which is supplemented by oral sources, both indigenous and Western; and written sources especially regarding descriptions of flora and fauna, which often referred to other continent.⁷ The inclusion of more or less extensive borrowings from earlier works is rather systematic in travel literature and concerns both texts and pictures, although the latter were included in the descriptions in rather limited numbers because they greatly increased the cost of the volume.⁸ De Marees's chronicle is one of the oldest and most complete and this was the reason why, along with Dapper's rich compilation of second-hand information (he has never been to Africa), it will be systematically quoted or, more or less extensively, copied by all subsequent travelogues focusing on West Africa.⁹

The presence of numerous plates was an important reason for the success of de Marees's work, because travel reports were rarely illustrated: while the iconographic apparatus embellished the text and increased its impact on the audience, it also made the book more expensive. The iconographic apparatus, when present, had a great impact, because in a very effective and immediate way it helped creating in the readers' imagination the visual model of what the texts told about the African *terra incognita*. Illustrations were so powerful not only because they were supposed to give the visual version of the text, but also because they had their own value as an independent medium. For this reason, they would remain as cultural and visual stereotypes until the threshold of the nineteenth century.¹⁰

De Marees is aware of the strong impact that images have on the reader: in the Dedication, he explains the meaning and purpose of the pictures. «I was on the Gold coast

⁴ De Marees 1604 and 1625. See Castaldo 2021.

⁵ L'Honoré Naber 1912.

⁶ I refer to the modern English translation by van Dantzig and Jones 1987, with some integration from the original Dutch version, almost concerning the definitions of musical instruments. Van Dantzig and Jones 1987: XVIII.

⁷ Van Dantzig and Jones 1987: XV-XVI; 3.

⁸ For the interpretation of pictures see: Hirschberg 1969: 10.

⁹ See for example Dapper 1668, Bosman 1794, Villault de Bellefond 1669, Lemaire 1695, Barbot 1732: they supplement in different ways first-hand information with passages from previous literature.

¹⁰ See also Inselin 1994: 165-166.

of Guinea and discovered that there was not description of this Coast [available]... I therefore applied myself with diligence, as far as was possible... to make a description thereof, to put everything in perfect order and adorn it with some handsome plates (*ende met sommige fraeye Fygueren te vercierren*), so that one might see of what shape or character the Men and Women are there in Guinea». ¹¹ Therefore, these pictures had both the function to inform the reader in a more direct and immediate way than words and to delight it, satisfying his esthetic demands. ¹² It was the publisher who decided how many illustrations had to be included in the book and in what format: for example, the illustrations in the *Description* are accompanied by detailed captions highlighting aspects that might interest the reader, following the model typically used by the Dutch publisher Cornelis Claesz. ¹³ The copperplates in de Marees's *Description* are quite consistent with the text, and therefore some scholars assumed that the engravings in de Marees's book were probably based on sketches made by the author himself during his trip. ¹⁴ However, there is no evidence that such drawings ever existed, neither by De Marees nor by any other authors who published travel accounts for Claesz. It is plausible to think that the publisher himself entrusted the creation of these plates to engravers active in the Netherlands at that time. They would have interpreted the text according to the artistic standards of sixteenth-century Netherlands, embellishing the books, making them more attractive, and thus more easily marketable. Therefore, the illustrators who created the plates had never seen the reality they were illustrating and they had to provide a visual representation of the information in the text without having any available iconographic model. ¹⁵ Consequently, they had to rely on the European visual models, in this case the sixteenth-century Netherlands and the classical world, which were well known to them: the result –images presenting exotic content through classical or generally Western figurative traditions– was necessarily very imaginative and far from reality. ¹⁶ One final consideration is that the plates in de Marees's *Description* are not taken from previous works but are original. In fact, images included in later travelogues are often copied from earlier texts, even if the latter focused on different topics. Sometimes these copies are not faithful to the originals, but have some variants: see the case of table 5 of the de Marees's Dutch edition, published in Amsterdam in 1617 by the printer Michiel Colijn, student and employee of Claesz. The plates of both the 1602 (Fig. 1a) and 1617 (Fig. 1b) editions are organized in a very similar way, but the differences are very clear: for example, the women dancing around the tree, represented in the original edition in the foreground, are seen from behind, while in the later edition they are depicted from the front, and the

¹¹ Van Dantzig and Jones 1987; Inselin 1994: 148-50.

¹² Sutton 2011.

¹³ Inselin 1994: 150-151.

¹⁴ Hirschberg 1969: 6; Inselin 1994: 152-53.

¹⁵ Sutton 2012: 88.

¹⁶ Sutton 2012: 74-76. Some further consideration on the way the native Africans were represented in Bassani 1987: 8-9.

drum player next to them is also depicted in a different position. Other plates in the 1617 edition, however, are unchanged: evidently the printer, in publishing the new edition of de Marees's *Description*, commissioned some plates from other artists who produced some personalized copies.

In the second part of his book de Marees describes some regions of Guinea: «We come now to the Kingdom of Guinea, which may be said to extend altogether over a distance of 500 miles, which is equivalent to about 400 Dutch miles.¹⁷ Everything from Rio de Benin to the Kingdom of Melly [Mali] is considered part of Guinea, even though there are a multitude of small Kingdom in between».¹⁸ Then, as an observer curious and intelligent and with less prejudices than many of his contemporaries, he provides a lot of information about the material culture, religious beliefs, political and social organization, economic system and general life style of the people living in these countries. Here and there we even find several annotations on music and musical instruments of the natives, some of which are accompanied by illustrations closely related to the text.¹⁹ Music accompanies some religious ceremonies, as a sacrifice to the gods, called by the natives "Fetissi", described in chapter 16: at the end of a ritual taking place in front of an altar, the priest stands up, sprinkles the altar with a liquid and utters some unknown words. Those attending the ceremony repeat the priest's words and clap their hands while shouting *Iou Iou...* (34a). They give gold to the priest to perform rites in honor of the god, so that the god will again grant them abundant fishing. The priest and his wives, elegantly dressed and adorned, go around the village weeping, beating their chests and clapping their hands with great clamor, as a sign of great mourning. Once they reach the beach, they encircle their necks with the branches of the trees they think are the deities who offer them fish, and the priest beats a drum in their honor... «Sorcerer or man who will exorcise the *Fetisso* comes with a drum and plays or beats it in front of the trees, which they keep for that purpose and consider to be good». (See Appendix: Text 1b)

Dances and drum music are described during ceremonies honoring their gods, which are even represented in the Plate 5 and described by a caption (see Appendix: Text 1a, Fig. 1): two women in the foreground are dancing beside a tree, while a man beside them beats with two sticks a high drum attached hanging from his shoulder: the body of the drum is rather conical, and with a skin stretched on its bigger end. On the right, there are three sitting people who are performing a ritual to ensure that the divinity may leave the dead in peace. A man attending the ritual is sitting while beating with two sticks a drum, smaller than the previous one. In this chapter, where de Marees describes the religion and the gods of the natives, he looks at these unfamiliar peoples with curiosity, not despising or putting them in ridicule. The presence of different types of drums is attested on other occasions, especially the military one, described in chapter 19. The

¹⁷ About 2500 Km.

¹⁸ De Marees 1602, ch. IV, 7b; van Dantzig and Jones 1987: 16.

¹⁹ Some short considerations in Hirschberg, 1969: 6-18.

battles take place to the sound of horns and drums: « the boys or servants carry into war drums on which they beat; others have horns made of elephant tusks (*olyphanten*) which they blow (See Appendix: Text 2).

At the end of the chapter, the author describes different types of instruments (see Appendix: Text 3): the first was made from a tree trunk and covered with a goatskin (he did not specify whether it was covered at only one end or both); it was very large, being 20 feet long, corresponding roughly to 6 meters, and was beaten with hooked sticks and used during particular ceremonies. These dimensions are probably exaggerated:²⁰ indeed it is possible that the text refers to a large drum called a *fontomfrom*, which can reach a length of 10 feet, about three meters. This is a drum of the “talking drum” type, still used in Ghana among the Asante people during royal ceremonies, not as a single instrument but in ensembles.²¹ Still today, the skin is stretched over the trunk by a system of laces attached to small wooden pins. The second type of drum is also made from a hollowed-out tree, it is smaller in size, with a circular upper end and a pointed lower end, and is the prerogative of nobles, who play it hanging around their necks. In the table 6, depicting a battle scene, a soldier in the background plays a drum attached to his shoulder which can perhaps be interpreted as this second type of drum (Fig. 2). A similar type is also depicted in the sacrifice scene in Plate 5 (Fig. 1a).

Other instruments are ivory trumpets, made from elephant tusks and decorated with engravings representing men and animals: they were played horizontally through a square hole drilled on the convex side (see Appendix: Text 3). Even this kind of horns, as the big drum mentioned above, had a special status: they were usually kept at the royal palace and only the king was allowed to possess them and to give the permission to play them.²² There are numerous examples of ivory trumpets showing similar organological features and decorations, coming from the regions of the Gulf of Guinea and dated to the 17th and 18th centuries.²³ And still today horns, similar to the old one, but without decorations, are frequently used in Ghana, for example during the Ashanti ceremonies.²⁴

Moreover, drums are played not only during the battle: in a situation of transgression of laws or to resolve a dispute, an officer goes to the villages, escorted by an assistant (a slave) playing the drum and by two boys beating with small sticks on a cow-bells without clapper (see Appendix: Text 5). This kind of idiophone is still in use in Africa, such as different kinds of bronze bells without clapper, beaten with wooden or metallic sticks, like the *gankogui* or the *agogo*.

The kind of horn mentioned in the text is used not only in military contexts, but also during ceremonies of different types: in chapter 20 de Marees describes the status of

²⁰ The Dutch feet was about 30 cm so that it should have been 6 meters long.

²¹ See Ampene 2020: 108, 112-66 (on drums), including a rich and updated bibliography.

²² This passage on musical instruments is cited almost literally by Dapper 1668: 485.

²³ Castaldo 2021: 74. See Fig. 7.

²⁴ Ampene 2020: 133-34.

the king, who is escorted by the guards playing horns in a sign of royal dignity, making also a consideration on the way they play together «in consonance with one another» (see Appendix: Text 4).

Music usually characterizes all festive moments and celebrations, such as the ceremony of investiture of the nobles described in Chapter 26 and illustrated by plate 15 (see Appendix: Text 6, Fig. 3), showing the candidate sitting on a chair, carried by servants and preceded by three musicians, one playing a drum fixed to his shoulder, and two blowing into the horn. In the background two groups of women are dancing while beating a kind of basin with sticks. In the center of the scene there is an ox, which during the ceremony is carried in a procession that ends with dances rhythmized by the sound of drums. The ceremony of investiture, which takes place in the village “market place” of the village is attended by warriors, with weapons and shields, and other men playing drums, horns, bells and other musical instruments.²⁵ Women dance while beating on a kind of basin that we also find in the in chapter 40, focusing on funeral rituals: the women take part to them singing, making big clamor and playing this kind of cymbals (see Appendix Texts 7a, 7b, Fig. 4).

The dances and musical instruments mentioned so far are systematically described in Chapter 37 focusing on the special interest of natives for dancing (see Appendix: Text 8).

Women meet in the evening to dance: they adorn themselves putting around their arms rings made of metal or ivory and around their legs rings with bells which resound during the dance.²⁶ They bring other instruments to accompany the dances: copper basins which they strike with wooden sticks, drums on which they sit down when they drum. Others have round blocks, cut out on all sides so that air can pass through them (?) and beaten with sticks: these too they strike with clappers. Others have cow-bells (without the clapper and beaten with a stick) and a harp with six strings made of reed, played with both hands, and everyone uses his own instruments, keeping in good tune with one another.

The instruments mentioned here were already cited in the previous chapter of the book, except the «round block with holes played with sticks», probably to be interpreted as a kind of gong; and a stringed instrument with 6 strings made of reed. De Marees clearly does not know how the natives call this instrument, so he defines it using the term “harp” related to a string instrument belonging to the Western tradition and more familiar to him. The “kind of harp” mentioned here may refer to a kind of harp-luth spread in Ghana, to be identified with the “seperewa-sanku”, still used in West Africa in present days (Fig. 5). The author does the same when he explains how the musicians relate each other and uses the expression «keeping in good tune with one another», thus referring to the concept of intonation, or “to play with tuned instruments”, a concept clearly belonging to the Western music culture. All these instruments are still in use today

²⁵ This passage on the ceremony of investiture of a nobleman is cited almost literally by Dapper 1668: 486.

²⁶ This detail is even mentioned in the texts 9 and 10 (see Appendix).

in West Africa: bells of different types played with wooden sticks, drums of all sizes played with hooked sticks or with hands, the harp-lute “seperewa-sanku”: perhaps only the way to play drums sitting on the instrument is less usual in these regions. We can notice the absence of the horns, which are not consistent in this context of feminine and informal leisure, being symbols of royal power

The chapter continues with a description of the dances: the women dance in pairs, jumping, stamping their feet on the floor, bringing their heads closer together from time to time to exchange a few words, snapping their fingers, and tapping a ponytail on their shoulders.²⁷ The *Description* does not include a plate illustrating this dance which is instead represented in a map of the regions of Senegambia and the western Gold Coast (Fig. 6a), by the Portuguese cartographer Luiz Teixeira, published in 1602 by Cornelis Claesz, the same publisher as de Marees’s book, who was a famous printer and merchant of geographic maps in Amsterdam at that time.²⁸

The inscription describing the regions illustrated in the map ends with the sentence: «published in the same year was a book with a more extensive description of these regions by P.D.M. (= Peter de Marees). The author clearly knew in a very detailed way the work of De Marees, since the two engravings on the top of the map are loosely related to the chapters 37 and 53 of his text.

The image on the top left (Fig. 6b), which recalls very thoroughly the de Marees passage, shows some women dancing in pairs, waving ponytails and bringing their faces close together to exchange words; some are wearing anklets of bells. The dances are accompanied by the sound of “basins” beaten with a stick and bells. On the right left, a man plays a harp with six strings and a second man sits on the top of a drum playing it with sticks. The caption details the scene by mentioning all the instruments in the image (see Appendix: Text 11a): once again the author appeals to Western culture when he defines the stringed instrument similar to the Western lyre («nostra testadini (sic) similia facta cytharae») as having a sound box made of turtle shell and strings of reed or horsehair from an elephant’s tail. It is even interesting to point out how the engraver visualizes this kind of African lute mentioned in the text as a coeval Western harp: since he did not know what the instrument described by the author looked like, it represents it as a stringed instrument very popular in the Western world and then familiar to him.

²⁷ Dapper quotes in his work the full passage: Dapper 1668: 471.

²⁸ «Effigies amplii Regni auriferi Guineae in Africa siti, extensum inde ad insulis Atlanticis, vulgo dictis, de Cabo Verde: ad flumen Benin, us[que], ad cuius ripam sita est Regia urbs et magna Benin, at[que] inde ad promontorium Lopi Gonsalvi delineata par S. Rovelasum, ex politioribus lineamentis figurata per Lodouicum Texeram, protocosmographum Regis Hispaniarum. Eodem anno editus est liber amplam horum regionum descriptionem continens, per P.D.M.» [*Detailed representations of the extensive gold-bearing Kingdom of Guinea, situated in Africa, extending to the Atlantic islands, commonly called Cape Verde, to the Benin River, on whose bank lies the royal and great city of Benin, and from there to the promontory of Lope Gonçalves, drawn by S. Rovelasum from more refined sketches by Ludovico Texera, chief cosmographer to the King of Spain. In the same year, a book containing a full description of these regions was published by P.D.M.*]. See also Boesjou 2005: 8-12. For the Teixeira map, see <<https://exhibits.stanford.edu/renaissance-exploration/catalog/wd588vc7077>>.

The picture on the top right shows some noblemen going to the court accompanied by numerous servants (Fig. 6c): they are naked, and sit on the horses like the women, with feet on the same side. Perhaps there is an intent here to ridicule them, because some are shown from behind, with their bottom in view. Some servants shelter the nobleman from the sun with a large umbrella, others follow them in procession playing various musical instruments: on the left, horns and a kind of beaten gong; on the right a drum, and a wind instrument to be identified perhaps as a flute. Again, the caption describes the scene in great detail (see Appendix: Text 12b), listing the instruments played during this occasion: flutes, mentioned here for the first time, drums, a type of hollow-shaped metal gong beaten with sticks, perhaps to be identified with the *agogo*,²⁹ and a small net full of rattles that, when shaken or tapped with the hands, «makes a noise as if the net were full of big nuts».³⁰ The latter instrument could be the early version of the *axatse*, an idiophone still widespread in the regions of West Africa, where it takes different names (*djabara*, *shekere*), and consisting of a small gourd, over which a net with beads is hung and by pulling this net up and down, a musical sound is produced.

The text of the caption is a free Latin translation of the Chapter 53 of the de Marees's book, where the author provides the description of Benin city through the words of the anonymous author D.R. (see Appendix: Text 11), but does not include any plate.³¹ In this case there is no precise correspondence between the image in the Teixeira map and the text it is meant to illustrate: in fact, the picture on one hand shows, among the other instruments, even the horns, whose symbolic value stresses the prestigious and powerful position of the nobles and which are not mentioned in the text; on the other, it does not represent the net with rattles which is listed instead. However, an illustration of this passage is included in the Latin translation of the *Description* published by De Bry in 1604 and showing a nobleman seated on a horse, accompanied by a small group of servants with drum, flute and the net with rattles (Fig. 7).³²

In conclusion, these accounts, seen through the filter of the Western point of view and its prejudices about the African culture, at that time still little known, are therefore particularly meaningful for the modern scholars, since they make it possible to recover

²⁹ A kind of bell externally struck with wooden sticks.

³⁰ It could be the early version of the calabash, a small gourd, over which a net with beads is hung and by pulling this net up and down, a musical sound is produced.

³¹ Some scholars identify the author whose initials are D.R. with Dietrick Ruiters: see van Dantzig and Jones 1987: 226, note 1.

³² de Marees 1604: Tav. XXIII: «partim tympana pulsant, partim cornibus & tibiis ludunt... serui enim ipsorum reticulis quibusdam instructi sunt, sacculos istos fenestratos siue cancellatos, quibus viri in forum piscarium apud nos egredientes vulgo utuntur, aemulantibus, his, nescio quid inclusum, si manibus pulsetur sonum edit, qualis solet esse nuçum in vasculo aliquo commotarum strepitusæ» [Some beat drums, others play horns and pipes... their slaves are equipped with certain nets, imitating those mesh or latticed bags with windows, which men commonly use when going to the fish market among us. These contain something inside – I'm not sure what – that, when shaken by hand, makes a sound like the rattle of nuts in a little container].

the historical dimension of the sound events studied in present times by ethnomusicologist, and they document some long lasting traditions living through the centuries. At the same time, the scholars can interpret these historical documents in the light of the still living musical traditions. Even the plates included in these travelogues have a great importance, although they are mostly unrealistic and fictional, since the engravers were not familiar with the realities they were representing. These pictures were meant to present facts in an easy and comprehensible way and to aid understanding by simplifying what was expressed verbally. They had the purpose to combine the didactic, informative function with beauty, pleasure, and entertainment, showing exotic content through visual models familiar to the readers. For this reason, the historical value of such illustrations should not be contested, but they cannot be considered as a primary ethnographic or ethnohistorical sources.³³

³³ Hirschberg 1969.

Appendix. Texts

1a.

van Dantzig and Jones 1987: Ch. 16, 33a, p. 66.

About their Sunday, they idolatrous beliefs and their idols, which they call Fetisso

(33a) *Description of the plate n. 5.* The picture shows how and in what manner they worship their *Fetisso* and what superstition they pay to their God (indulging in frivolity instead of paying reverence). *A.* shows a *Fetissero* or one of their Priests standing by a Tree with his two Wives, worshipping their God and indulging in much frivolity, standing and playing Drums [*staende met Trommels en spelen*]. His Wives are jumping face to face, dressed in their Sunday best; and thus they greatly enjoy themselves together, in honour of their *Fetisso*...*B.* shows them performing another prayer, praying to their God...*C.* shows their ordinary articles of Sorcery, which they use to exorcise something and to ensure that the *Fetisso* may leave the dead in peace.

1b.

van Dantzig and Jones 1987: Ch 16, 34b, p. 69

(34b) Sorcerer or man who will exorcise the *Fetisso* comes with a Drum and plays or beats it in front of the trees [*comt met een Trommel, ende speelt oft clopt voor de Boomen*], which they keep for that purpose and consider to be good.

2.

van Dantzig and Jones 1987: Ch 19, 45a, pp. 89-90.

About the wars among the towns, how they conduct themselves in them and act, and the kinds of Weapons they use in war

(45a) when the warriors are fighting the boys or servants carry into war drums on which they beat; others have horns made of elephant tusks which they blow (*De Knapen ofte Dienaers voeren de Trommels inden krijgh, daer sy op slaen en trommelen, andre hebben Horens van Oliphants tanden, daer sy op blasen*) ... The Warriors fighting each other in the field do their best to destroy the enemy... The Drums and Horns are beaten and blown (*de Trommels ende Horens worden gheroert ende gheblasen*)

3.

van Dantzig and Jones 1987: Ch. 19, 47a, p. 93.

About the wars among the towns, how they conduct themselves in them and act, and the kinds of weapons they use in war

(47a) They make their drums (*Trommels*) out of hollow trees, stretch a buck's skin over them with wooden pins and play on them with drumsticks which look like ladles. These drums (*Trommels*) are usually deposited in front of the courtyard of the king's captain and guards and are sometimes no less than twenty foot (*voeten*) long; they are played when

the king holds certain festivities. They also make smaller drums (*cleynder Trommels*) out of hollow trees: these they hung around their necks and go and play them in town. These drums are round at the top and taper sharply at the bottom, just like a spinning top (*Dese Trommels zijn boven ront, ende onder heel scherp, als een Tol*). No one except those of noble rank is allowed to use them. Furthermore, they make horn out of elephant tusks (*Hoorens van Oliphants tanden*), which they decorate nicely with incisions and other things. In the middle of the horn, they cut a square hole, through which they blow; but nobody is allowed to use these instruments except the king or the captain.

4.

van Dantzig and Jones 1987: Ch. 20, 48a-48b, p. 95.

About the status of the kings and what honour is paid to them

(48a) All these festivals they indulge in a lot of Monkey-games, such as fencing and drumming, singing and jumping. The women enjoy themselves on these occasions by dancing. Each King celebrates his Festival separately, one celebration being held shortly after the other... (The king) when he goes out is protected by his guard, which surrounds him. Early in the morning and late in the evening the slaves play on those horns made of elephant teeth (*Slaven op dese Horens van Oliphants tanden*) (48b) which made a curious sound as they suck in and blow out the air, in consonance with one another.

5.

van Dantzig and Jones 1987: Ch 22, 51a, p. 101.

About their Laws and manner of exercising Justice

(51a) They also keep strict Laws...If it suits them to expose somebody, they tell the captain, who at once has the drum (*Trommel*) beaten by the *Catiff*. The latter goes around the town with a drum around his neck, accompanied by two other boys, each of whom has in his hand a cow-bell without a clapper, which they strike with a little stick clapper (*een Koe-bel inde handt, sonder clepel, ende spelen daer op met een houtken*).

6.

van Dantzig and Jones 1987: Ch. 36, 85a-85b, p. 167.

About their nobility, and how they make one another nobleman, what kind of ceremonies they have for this, and so on

(85a) *Description of plate 15*. In this picture, drawn from the life, you may see in what manner and with kind of triumphal ceremony they make a nobleman, who gives away all his goods to the people in order to be a Nobleman. On such occasions the women enjoy themselves greatly, dancing and capering, and the men too, fencing and fighting. They do this for three days, after which they go and kill the cow...and quarter it... (85b) *Letter E*. represents the women, who go ahead of them, *F* are the womenfolk who beat basins and play other (musical) instruments (*is het vrouw volck die op de Beckens ende andere Instrumenten spelen ende cloppen*).

7a.

van Dantzig and Jones: Ch 40, 90a-90b, p. 179.

About the manner in which they bewail their deceased, with visits by friends; the clamour they make singing and striking cymbals (Becken slaen) ...

(90a) *Description of plate 16 (= 17)*. In this picture what ceremonies they perform when they bury the dead. ... (90b) *B.* shows their way of mourning and the people who take the deceased for burial. The ones in front prance along, playing cymbals (*spelende op Beckens*); the other follow the Corpse and do nothing but wait and make a great clamour. *C.* When the deceased has been buried in the grave, the women crawl back and forth over the grave and make a great clamour.

7b.

van Dantzig and Jones 1987: Ch 40, 91b, p. 181

(91b) Meanwhile the friends or neighbors come to visit the deceased and lament his misfortune. Others, such as close friends, or such as the women, take up position around the house and sing and strike basins, from time to time going to look at the deceased: they go around him singing and capering, clapping their hands and making a great tumult. Then they go around the house, singing and playing their basins...

8.

van Dantzig and Jones 1987: Ch 37, 87a-87b, pp. 171-172

About their dancing and capering and what are their rules in it

(87a) They adorn themselves very splendidly, especially the women, when they are going to dance, and they are very proud of their appearance. They put around their arms many Bangles of Copper, Pewter and Ivory; around their legs they put rings of bells, so that they may sound whilst they are dancing (*Ringhen daer Bellen aen zijn, om dat die int dansen clincken souden*). ... (87b) Generally they assemble in the evening and go to the Market-place in order to dance there. Some have instruments with them on which they play, such as copper basins which they strike with wooden clappers (*copere Beckens, ende cloppen daer op met houtte Clippels*), or wooden drums (*Trommel*) cut from hollow tree, over which a *cabriet's* skin is stretched and on which they sit down when they drum; ... others have round blocks, cut out on all sides so that air can pass through them (*de derde hebben ronde blocken, zijnde rontsom doorluchtich ghesneden*): these too they strike with clappers (sticks). Others have cow-bells (*oe-bellen*) and again a harp with 6 strings made of reed, played with both hands. Thus each uses his own instrument, keeping in good tune with one another (een Harp met 6. Snaren van Riet, spelende daer op met beyde handen, ende een ieder gebruyct daer zijn Instrumenten, houwende goede resonantie op malcanderens spel).

Other sing or begin to dance with one another, jumping on pairs opposite each other and stamping their feet on the ground, snapping their fingers in the air, bending their heads together, sometimes speaking to one another. In their hands they have horsetails which

they cast on one shoulder, then on the other, keeping time the music and one another's steps, each doing the same as the other. Other women take straw-wisps, which they let drop to the ground, and then they jump in, throwing them up again with their feet and catching them with their hands.

... There are also houses where young men learn to dance and to make music

9.

van Dantzig and Jones 1987: Ch. 7, 19a, p. 38.

How the women comport themselves and how they dress

(19a) A loose woman or Whore (called *Etigafou*) often wears copper rings with Bells on her legs, and these clang as she goes through the streets.

10.

van Dantzig and Jone 1987: Ch 39, 88b, p. 175.

About their hatred and envy for one another and the fact that one finds no beggars there

(88b) *Description of the plate 16. B.* is a woman of easy virtue, called *Etigrafo*; she too is very nicely attired. Her face is cut and punctured and around the ankles she has Rings with bells, which sound every time she walks or dances.

11.

van Dantzig and Jones 1987: Ch. [53], 115a, 116b, 117b, pp. 226, 228-29, 230.

(115a) *Description of the situation and the character of the Great city of Benin, situated in the first Bight inlet*

(116b) The king also has very many noblemen. When a nobleman comes to court, he comes on horseback. They sit on their horses as the women do in our country, and on both sides they have a man to whom they hold on. They have as many servants walking behind them as befits their status. Some servants have great shields with which they protect the nobleman against the sun and they go alongside the nobleman ... The others follow behind, making music: some play drums, others horns and flutes, and some have a hollow piece of iron on which they beat (*sommige op Trommelen, sommige op Hoorens en Fluyten, ende sommige hebben een hol Yser, daer cloppense al op.*) The horse is led by one man and thus he rides the court, accompanied by music. The very great nobleman do something different when they ride to court: they have little nets, of kind with which men in our country go to the fish-market and this little net I filled with thigs which they tap with their hands, so that they rattle as if the little net were filled with big nuts (*daer de Mans in ons Landt mede op de Vis-merct gaen, dat Netgen is met eenige dingen gevult, daer cloppense doorgaens met de handt tegen dattet rammelt, al even eens oft sulcken Netken met groote Noten gevult ware, ende datmen daer met de handt teghen clopte 4*): een Edelman heeft veel Knechts die achter hem loopen met sulcke Netten). A nobleman has many servants who go behind him with such a nets.

(117b) p. 230 *About the nobleman and their wives*. It is with great reverence that the nobleman go to court, having with them various kinds of musical instruments to play and they are accompanied by many other negroes, some having drums, on which they play, and others playing others instruments. They place on the back of the horse a small wooden chair and around the neck of the horse they hang a cow bell, which rings as the horse proceeds. Two people also walk alongside the nobleman, and he leans on them with his arms. ...their horses are very small... The captain has a number of soldiers under his command and will always go in the midst of his soldiers, surrounded by other people who accompany them leaping, singing and having lot of fun.

12a.

Luis Teixeira, map of Senegambia, Amsterdam, Claesz, 1602.

Caption of picture 1. The dances with which the Guineans enjoy themselves thoroughly are of this kind. On their arms and legs they have very many rings of copper, pewter and ivory; many of them are equipped with little bells, producing various sounds. The instruments they use to make music include basins, drums, hollowed cylindrical trunks, cowbells, and some instruments similar to our lyres, made of tortoiseshell, whose strings are composed of certain reeds or the bristles of an elephant's tail. They generally caper and stamp their feet alternately on the ground, intermingling this with various histrionic gestures. They do not like performing the dances in the presence of strangers.

Communes Guincitarum choreae quibus summon pere (sic) delectantur, hoc modo fuerunt, in brachys et cruribus quam plurimos habent vel ereos, vel staneos, vel eburneos annubos (sic) quorum plearibus tintinnabulis muniti sunt, varium ex motu edentes tinnitum. Instrumenta quibus canunt sunt pelves, tympana, trunci teretes cavati, nolae vaccariae, quaedam nostra testadini (sic) similia facta cytharae quarum chordae ex certis arundinibus, aut setis caudae Elephantinae composita sunt. Quorum sonus non injucundus est. Bini plaerumque saltant, alterno pede terram quatientes, diversis gestibus histrionicis intermixtis; Inviti choreas praesentibus extranei agunt.

12b.

Luis Teixeira, map of Senegambia, Amsterdam, Claesz, 1602.

Caption of picture 2. It is customary for noble courtiers in the royal city of Benin, when they go to court, to ride crosswise like our women, sitting on saddles instead of on cushions, with their feet hanging down, and supported on either side by two servants; they are accompanied by numerous servants, one of whom carries an umbrella against the sun's rays over their heads, others follow playing flutes, drums, and iron plates which they strike, and so they enter the court. The magnates use nets full of rattles, which are rung by the servants, and the King has his own style of great display and pomp.

Mos est Nobilibus aulicis in Regia urbe Benin, aulam adituris, equitare trans versim foeminarum nostratium more sediculis loco ephippiorum insidentes, pendulis pedibus, et duobus

famulis utrinque suffulei; plurimis comitati famulis, quorum unus umbraculum adversus puncturam solis, supra caput gestat, alii sequuntur canetes (sic) tibiis, tympanis ferries tabulis quos pulsant, atque ita Regiam ingrediuntur. Magnates utuntur retibus tintinnabulis plenis, quae a famulis pulsantur, Rex suo more magno apparatu et pompa utitur.

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FIGURE 1A. Ceremonies in honour of the African divinities (*Fetissi*). De Marées 1602, plate n. 5 («About their Sunday, their Idolatrous beliefs and their Idols which they call *Fetissi*»). Dantzig and Jones 1987, p. 56.

FIGURE 1B. Ceremonies in honour of the African divinities (“Fetissi”). Pieter De Marées, *Beschryvinge ende historische verhael vant Gout Koninckrijk van Guinea*, Amsterdam, Michiel Colijn, 1617, Plate n. 5.

FIGURE 2. Three warriors and a battle scene in the background: on the right a soldier plays a drum attached to his shoulder. De Marees 1602, plate n. 6 («About the wars among the towns, how they conduct themselves in them and act, and the kinds of Weapons they use in war»). Dantzig and Jones 1987, p. 88.

FIGURE 3. Ceremony of investiture of the nobles. De Marees 1602, plate n. 15 («About their Nobility and how they make one another Nobleman, what kind of ceremonies they have for this, and so on»). Dantzig and Jones 1987, p. 167.

FIGURE 4. Funeral ritual: some women dance while beating on a kind of basin. De Marees 1602, plate n. 16 (=17) («About the manner in which they bewail their deceased, and which visits by friends; the clamor they make singing and striking cymbals [...]»). Dantzig and Jones 1987, p. 179.

FIGURE 5. Seperewa-sanku, instrument given by Thomas Bowdich, the British Ambassador at the Asanthe court, to the British Museum in 1818 (British Museum, Af1818, 1114.10).

FIGURE 6A. Map of Senegambia by Portuguese cartographer Luis Teixeira (Amsterdam, Claesz, 1602). Copy by Baptista van Doetichum (Amsterdam, 1660).

FIGURE 6B. Women dancing. Map of Senegambia by Portuguese cartographer Luis Teixeira (1602). Detail.

FIGURE 6C. Noblemen going to the court accompanied by numerous servants, some of them with musical instruments. Map of Senegambia by Portuguese cartographer Luis Teixeira (1602). Detail.

FIGURE 7. Nobleman seated on a horse, accompanied by a small group of servants some of them with musical instruments. De Mareis 1604, XXIII.